

Supplementary Material for:
**Local fermion density in inhomogeneous free-fermion chains:
a discrete WKB approach**

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In this Supplementary Material we present a detailed computation of the fermionic density of the Rindler chain for several values of its parameter.

The Rindler chain

The chain¹ (2) with parameters

$$J_n = J_0 \frac{n}{N}, \quad B_n = 0$$

was introduced in ref. [2] and referred to as the Rindler chain, since its associated space-time metric $ds^2 = J(x)^2 dt^2 - dx^2$ is the Rindler metric (i.e., the metric of two-dimensional Minkowski space as perceived by a uniformly accelerated observer). We shall take, for convenience, $J_0 = 1/2$, and add a linear magnetic field $B_n = bn/N$, so that the continuum limit of the chain's parameters reads

$$J(x) = \frac{x}{2\ell}, \quad B(x) = \frac{bx}{\ell}, \quad (S1)$$

with b a real parameter.

To begin with,

$$\xi(x, \varepsilon; b) = \frac{\ell\varepsilon - bx}{x} = -\xi(x, -\varepsilon; -b)$$

implies, by eq. (50), that

$$a\rho(x, \varepsilon; b) = 1 - a\rho(x, -\varepsilon, -b).$$

(In fact, a similar relation can be proved for the discrete average occupation numbers $\langle c_n^\dagger c_n \rangle$.) We may therefore assume, without loss of generality, that $b \geq 0$. In what follows we will discuss the three cases $b = 0$ (the original Rindler chain), $b = 1$, and $b > 1$ (the case $0 < b < 1$ is qualitatively similar to $b = 0$).

1. $b = 0$

From fig. 1 and eq. (50) it follows that there is a single depletion interval (for $\varepsilon < 0$) or saturation interval (for $\varepsilon > 0$) $[0, x_1(\varepsilon)]$, where $x_1(\varepsilon) = \ell |\varepsilon|$. The normalization constant in eq. (35b) is easily computed:

$$A(\varepsilon)^{-2} = \int_{\ell|\varepsilon|}^{\ell} \frac{dx}{\sqrt{4J^2(x) - \varepsilon^2}} = \int_{\ell|\varepsilon|}^{\ell} \frac{dx}{\sqrt{\frac{x^2}{\ell^2} - \varepsilon^2}} = \ell \operatorname{arccosh}(1/|\varepsilon|).$$

¹In what follows, equation numbers in arabic refer to the body of the paper (ref. [1]). All other figure and equation numbers refer to this Supplementary Material.

Figure 1: Plot of $B(x) \pm 2J(x)$ for the Rindler chain with $b = 0$ (left), $b = 1$ (center), and $b > 1$ (right).

By eq. (36), the equation of the envelopes of the WKB single-particle eigenfunctions is

$$y = \sqrt{2} \left(\operatorname{arccosh}(1/|\varepsilon|) \right)^{-1/2} (x^2 - \ell \varepsilon^2)^{-1/4} \Theta(x - \ell |\varepsilon|).$$

We shall next compute the approximation (47) to the filling fraction as a function of the Fermi energy ε_F . By the particle-hole symmetry due to the vanishing of the magnetic field (cf. remark 4.4 in the main text), we can restrict ourselves to Fermi energies $\varepsilon_F \leq 0$, and write

$$\nu(\varepsilon_F) = \frac{1}{\pi \ell} \int_{\ell |\varepsilon_F|}^{\ell} dx \arccos\left(\frac{|\varepsilon_F|}{x/\ell}\right) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{|\varepsilon_F|}^1 ds \arccos\left(\frac{|\varepsilon_F|}{s}\right).$$

The integral is easily evaluated by the standard change of variables $|\varepsilon_F|/s = \cos u$, followed by an integration by parts, with the result

$$\nu(\varepsilon_F) = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\arccos(-\varepsilon_F) + \varepsilon_F \operatorname{arccosh}(1/|\varepsilon_F|) \right). \quad (\text{S2})$$

Using the symmetry (53) we easily deduce that the above formula is actually valid for both positive and negative Fermi energies. In particular, for $\varepsilon_F = 0$ (half-filling) we obtain $\nu(0) = 1/2$, as expected.

Finally, for $\varepsilon_F \leq 0$ the WKB approximation to the fermion density is given by

$$a\rho(x, \varepsilon_F) = \frac{1}{\pi} \arccos\left(\frac{\ell |\varepsilon_F|}{x}\right) \Theta(x - \ell |\varepsilon_F|), \quad \varepsilon_F \leq 0,$$

while (again by eq. (53)) $a\rho(x, \varepsilon_F) = 1 - a\rho(x, -\varepsilon_F)$ for $\varepsilon_F > 0$. In other words, for all $\varepsilon_F \in [-1, 1]$ we have

$$a\rho(x, \varepsilon_F) = \Theta(\varepsilon_F) + \frac{1}{\pi} \arccos\left(-\frac{\ell \varepsilon_F}{x}\right) \Theta(x - \ell |\varepsilon_F|). \quad (\text{S3})$$

2. $b = 1$

In this case

$$B(x) - 2J(x) = 0, \quad B(x) + 2J(x) = \frac{2x}{\ell},$$

and hence, according to eqs. (32) and (33), the single-particle spectrum is contained in the interval $[0, 2]$. In this case the WKB eigenfunctions with energy ε vanish on

the interval $[0, \ell\varepsilon/2]$. Moreover, since $B(x) - 2J(x)$ is identically zero, the interval $[0, \ell\varepsilon_F/2]$ is a *saturation* interval for any Fermi energy ε_F (cf. the discussion at the end of section 4 in the main text). The normalization constant in this case is given by

$$A(\varepsilon)^{-2} = \int_{\ell\varepsilon/2}^{\ell} \frac{dx}{\sqrt{\frac{x^2}{\ell^2} - (\varepsilon - \frac{x}{\ell})^2}} = \ell \int_{\varepsilon/2}^1 \frac{ds}{\sqrt{\varepsilon(2s - \varepsilon)}} = \ell \sqrt{\frac{2}{\varepsilon} - 1}.$$

The equation of the envelopes of the WKB eigenfunctions is accordingly

$$y = \pm \left[\ell \left(1 - \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \right) \left(x - \frac{\ell\varepsilon}{2} \right) \right]^{-1/4} \Theta \left(x - \frac{\ell\varepsilon}{2} \right).$$

Since in this case $\xi^*(x, \varepsilon) = 1$ inside the saturation interval $[0, \ell\varepsilon/2]$, the WKB approximation to the filling fraction $\nu(\varepsilon_F)$ is given by

$$\nu(\varepsilon_F) = \frac{1}{\pi\ell} \cdot \frac{\pi\ell\varepsilon_F}{2} + \frac{1}{\pi\ell} \int_{\ell\varepsilon_F/2}^{\ell} dx \arccos \left(\frac{x/\ell - \varepsilon_F}{x/\ell} \right) = \frac{\varepsilon_F}{2} + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\varepsilon_F/2}^1 ds \arccos \left(1 - \frac{\varepsilon_F}{s} \right).$$

The integral can be again evaluated by a change of variable followed by integration by parts. After straightforward simplifications we thus obtain

$$\nu(\varepsilon_F) = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\arccos(1 - \varepsilon_F) + \sqrt{\varepsilon_F(2 - \varepsilon_F)} \right). \quad (\text{S4})$$

Finally, for all Fermi energies $\varepsilon_F \in [0, 2]$ the WKB approximation to the fermionic density now reads

$$a\rho(x, \varepsilon_F) = \Theta \left(\frac{\ell\varepsilon_F}{2} - x \right) + \frac{1}{\pi} \arccos \left(1 - \frac{\ell\varepsilon_F}{x} \right) \Theta \left(x - \frac{\ell\varepsilon_F}{2} \right). \quad (\text{S5})$$

3. $b > 1$

Finally, for $b > 1$ the plot of $B(x) \pm 2J(x)$ is as presented in fig. 1 (right); in particular, in this case the single-particle spectrum lies on the interval $[0, b + 1]$. It is apparent from this figure that the behavior of the filling fraction $\nu(\varepsilon_F)$ and the fermionic density $\rho(x, \varepsilon_F)$ depends on whether ε_F is less or greater than the critical value $B(\ell) - 2J(\ell) = b - 1$. The same is true for the normalization constant $A(\varepsilon)$. For instance, for $0 \leq \varepsilon < b - 1$ the two turning points are

$$x_1(\varepsilon) = \frac{\ell\varepsilon}{b+1}, \quad x_2(\varepsilon) = \frac{\ell\varepsilon}{b-1}, \quad (\text{S6})$$

and therefore

$$A(\varepsilon)^{-2} = \int_{x_1(\varepsilon)}^{x_2(\varepsilon)} \frac{dx}{\sqrt{\frac{x^2}{\ell^2} - (\varepsilon - \frac{bx}{\ell})^2}} = \frac{\ell}{\sqrt{b^2 - 1}} \int_{x_1(\varepsilon)}^{x_2(\varepsilon)} \frac{dx}{\sqrt{(x - x_1(\varepsilon))(x_2(\varepsilon) - x)}} = \frac{\pi\ell}{\sqrt{b^2 - 1}}.$$

In particular, the equation of the envelopes of the WKB wave functions is in this case

$$y = \pm \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \left[(x - x_1(\varepsilon))(x_2(\varepsilon) - x) \right]^{-1/4}.$$

Figure 2: Filling fractions $\nu(\varepsilon_F)$ for the Rindler chain with $b = 0, 1, 2$ and $N = 400$ spins (blue markers) compared to their WKB approximations (S2), (S4), and (S7) (continuous red line). In particular, note the linear growth of $\nu(\varepsilon_F)$ with $b = 2$ over the interval $0 \leq \varepsilon_F \leq b - 1 = 1$, in full agreement with eq. (S7a).

On the other hand, for $b - 1 \leq \varepsilon \leq b + 1$ there is a single turning point $x_1(\varepsilon)$, and hence

$$\begin{aligned} A(\varepsilon)^{-2} &= \int_{x_1(\varepsilon)}^{\ell} \frac{dx}{\sqrt{\frac{x^2}{\ell^2} - (\varepsilon - \frac{bx}{\ell})^2}} = \frac{\ell}{\sqrt{b^2 - 1}} \int_{\frac{\varepsilon}{b+1}}^1 \frac{ds}{\sqrt{(s - \frac{\varepsilon}{b+1})(\frac{\varepsilon}{b-1} - s)}} \\ &= \frac{\ell}{\sqrt{b^2 - 1}} \left[\frac{\pi}{2} + \arcsin\left(\frac{b^2 - 1}{\varepsilon} - b\right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

The equation of the WKB envelopes is now

$$y = \pm \sqrt{2} \left[\frac{\pi}{2} + \arcsin\left(\frac{b^2 - 1}{\varepsilon} - b\right) \right]^{-1/2} \left[\left(x - \frac{\ell\varepsilon}{b+1}\right) \left(\frac{\ell\varepsilon}{b-1} - x\right) \right]^{-1/4}.$$

Let us turn next to the WKB approximation to the filling fraction. From fig. 1 (right) it is apparent that $\xi^*(x, \varepsilon_F) = 1$ for $0 \leq x \leq x_1(\varepsilon_F)$, while $\xi^*(x, \varepsilon_F) = -1$ for $x_2(\varepsilon_F) \leq x \leq \ell$ when $\varepsilon_F \in [0, b - 1]$. We thus have

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(\varepsilon_F) &= \frac{x_1(\varepsilon_F)}{\pi\ell} + \frac{1}{\pi\ell} \int_{x_1(\varepsilon_F)}^{\min(x_2(\varepsilon_F), \ell)} dx \arccos\left(b - \frac{\ell\varepsilon_F}{x}\right) \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon_F}{\pi(b+1)} + \frac{\varepsilon_F}{\pi} \int_{t_0(\varepsilon_F)}^{\pi} dt \frac{t \sin t}{(b - \cos t)^2}, \end{aligned}$$

where $t_0(\varepsilon) = 0$ for $0 \leq \varepsilon \leq b - 1$ and $t_0(\varepsilon) = \arccos(b - \varepsilon)$ for $b - 1 \leq \varepsilon \leq b + 1$. Integrating by parts and simplifying the boundary term we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(\varepsilon_F) &= \frac{\varepsilon_F}{\pi} \frac{t_0(\varepsilon_F)}{b - \cos t_0(\varepsilon_F)} + \frac{\varepsilon_F}{\pi} \int_{t_0(\varepsilon_F)}^{\pi} \frac{dt}{b - \cos t} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon_F}{\pi} \frac{t_0(\varepsilon_F)}{b - \cos t_0(\varepsilon_F)} + \frac{2\varepsilon_F}{\pi\sqrt{b^2 - 1}} \arctan\left(\sqrt{\frac{b+1}{b-1}} \tan\left(\frac{t}{2}\right)\right) \Big|_{t_0(\varepsilon_F)}^{\pi} \\ &= \frac{\varepsilon_F}{\pi} \frac{t_0(\varepsilon_F)}{b - \cos t_0(\varepsilon_F)} + \frac{\varepsilon_F}{\sqrt{b^2 - 1}} - \frac{2\varepsilon_F}{\pi\sqrt{b^2 - 1}} \arctan\left(\sqrt{\frac{b+1}{b-1}} \tan\left(\frac{t_0(\varepsilon_F)}{2}\right)\right). \end{aligned}$$

Hence for $0 \leq \varepsilon_F \leq b - 1$ we have

$$\nu(\varepsilon_F) = \frac{\varepsilon_F}{\sqrt{b^2 - 1}}, \quad (\text{S7a})$$

while for $b - 1 \leq \varepsilon_F \leq b + 1$

$$\nu(\varepsilon_F) = \frac{\varepsilon_F}{\sqrt{b^2 - 1}} + \frac{1}{\pi} \arccos(b - \varepsilon_F) - \frac{2\varepsilon_F}{\pi\sqrt{b^2 - 1}} \arctan\left(\sqrt{\frac{(b+1)(1-b+\varepsilon_F)}{(b-1)(1+b-\varepsilon_F)}}\right). \quad (\text{S7b})$$

Figure 3: Left column: local fermion density for the Rindler chain with $N = 400$ spins, and several values of the parameter b and the filling fraction ν (blue markers) compared to their WKB approximations (S3), (S5), and (S8) (red line). Right column: plot of the corresponding single-particle eigenfunctions $\phi_n(\varepsilon)$ with energies $\varepsilon = N\nu$ (in blue) compared to their WKB envelopes (red lines).

Finally, from fig. 1 (right) and eq. (50) we deduce that

$$a\rho(x, \varepsilon_F) = 1, \quad 0 \leq x \leq x_1(\varepsilon_F) = \frac{\ell \varepsilon_F}{b+1},$$

for Fermi energies $\varepsilon_F \in [0, b+1]$. Moreover, for $0 \leq \varepsilon_F \leq b-1$ we have

$$\rho(x, \varepsilon_F) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\pi a} \arccos\left(b - \frac{\ell \varepsilon_F}{x}\right), & \frac{\ell \varepsilon_F}{b+1} \leq x \leq \frac{\ell \varepsilon_F}{b-1}, \\ 0, & \frac{\ell \varepsilon_F}{b-1} \leq x \leq \ell, \end{cases} \quad (\text{S8a})$$

while for $b-1 \leq \varepsilon_F \leq b+1$ the depletion interval at the chain's right end disappears, i.e.,

$$a\rho(x, \varepsilon_F) = \frac{1}{\pi} \arccos\left(b - \frac{\ell \varepsilon_F}{x}\right), \quad \frac{\ell \varepsilon_F}{b+1} \leq x \leq \ell. \quad (\text{S8b})$$

As can be seen from figs. 2 and 3, the agreement of the WKB approximations derived above with the numerical results is excellent across the full range of values of the parameter b and the filling fraction ν (or the single-particle energy ε).

References

- [1] M. Zapata, F. Finkel and A. González-López, *Local fermion density in inhomogeneous free-fermion chains: a discrete WKB approach*, submitted to SciPost Phys.
- [2] B. Mula, N. Samos Sáenz de Buruaga, G. Sierra, S. N. Santalla and J. Rodríguez-Laguna, *Depletion in fermionic chains with inhomogeneous hoppings*, Phys. Rev. B **106**, 224204(10) (2022), doi:[10.1103/PhysRevB.106.224204](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.106.224204).